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**CHALLENGES IN THE USE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY IN
AGRICULTURAL EDUCATION AND TRAINING IN COLLEGES OF EDUCATION IN ADAMAWA
STATE**

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Abstract

The study was conducted to ascertain the challenges in the use of ICT in Agricultural Education and Training in Colleges of Education in Adamawa State. Three objectives guided the study, the objectives were translated into three research questions and two corresponding null hypotheses. Frequency count was used to answer research question one, mean and standard deviation were used to answer research question two and three, and t-test statistic was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study used descriptive research design and questionnaire was used to solicit for responses from the respondents. The instrument for data collection was subjected to face and content validity by 1 expert in the Department of Vocational Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola and 3 experts from the Department of Vocational and Technical Education, Adamawa State University, Mubi. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to test the reliability of the instrument and a reliability coefficient of 0.76 was obtained through test re-test test method. Results from the study revealed that; ICT facilities are not available in state owned college of education, Agricultural Education lecturers have positive attitude towards the use of ICT facilities in teaching in agricultural education and training. Based on the findings of the study, recommendations were made among which: Colleges of Education in the state should organize training on the use of ICT for all lecturers including those in Agricultural Education programme.

Keywords: Challenges, ICT, Agricultural Education, Colleges of Education

Introduction

The success of any educational programme in Nigeria and the world at large depends on the availability of resources, both human and material for proper implementation of the programme. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is one of the resources that when made available, has a significant role to play on the outcome of educational programme in various institutions of learning especially colleges of education that are saddled with the responsibility of teacher training in Nigeria. The rapid growth and development of ICTs offers a good opportunity to educational institutions to enhance the teaching and training process at all levels of education which will enhance learning. Use of ICT led to reform in the teaching and transformation in various sectors of Nigeria economy such as Agriculture, Medicine, Engineering and so on (Ahmed, 2016; Talibian et al, 2014; and Toro, 2012)

Nowadays, especially during the Covid 19 Pandemic, teachers at all levels of education are confronted with rapidly changing demands on their profession which requires sophisticated and wider set of skills in ICT. Research at various levels confirmed that teachers with ICT competencies who have confidence in Information Technology are source of inspiration to their students and contribute to professional and personal development of students (Mynarikova & Novotny, 2021; Siddiquah & Salim, 2017 and Ibe, 2021). ICT provides opportunities for lecturers and students to operate, store, manipulate and also retrieve information, encourage independent and active learning and self-responsibility for learning, motivate lecturers and students to continue even outside school premises and hours, plan and prepare lessons, design materials and facilitate sharing of resources and expertise (Habibu et al, 2012).

Agricultural Education is one area that requires ICT due to some improvement brought about by ICT in the agricultural sector of many developed and developing nations like Nigeria. ICT has created advancement in agricultural information, agricultural development, agricultural value chain and agri-preneurship opportunities to provide better agricultural services, enhanced information dissemination through computer based advisory services both online and offline. Despite the role ICT plays, there is poor or inadequate availability of interactive multimedia, self-learning modules and online class courses in agricultural education domain (Anandaraja et al, 2015). Agriculture provides food and raw materials to various industries apart from being a primary source of employment to many people, educated and non-educated in Nigeria. Any improvement in agricultural activity has a positive impact on the farmers and the country at large. ICT is such an area that can bring about the needed improvement in terms of training or teaching to both farmers and students.

Ogunbodede et al (2020) observed that ICT facilities play an important role in the development of positive attitude towards the usage of the facilities in tertiary institutions of learning. Ogunbodede et al further opined that the utilization of ICT and internet services in tertiary institutions has opened the door to new ways of teaching and also carrying out research, and also, internet availability and usage has a positive impact on attitude of lecturers towards their academic activities. He however noted that despite the role ICT plays in education, accessibility and use of ICT and internet services are affected by so many constraints all of which impact on the value of teaching and research in tertiary institutions. Among the constraints are: poor electricity supply, lack of adequate ICT facilities, lack of appropriate internet facilities, inadequate information retrieval skills and negative attitude of staff.

The need to integrate ICT as a means of instruction in colleges of education has become necessary in view of the demands on graduates of colleges of education at both State and Federal level in Nigeria are ICT literate to cope with the global phenomena. The Federal Republic of Nigeria recognizes the role of ICT in teaching and learning atmosphere by launching in 2004 Education for all (EFA) and Millennium Development Goal (MDG) through the Federal Ministry of Education to make e-learning as part of mode of instruction in the education sector. Since ICT is any arrangement that is capable of capturing, manipulating, transmitting or receiving, storing or retrieving information or data, it has roles to play in education and training of students as well as famers in best agricultural practices (Bede et al, 2015). Information and Communication Technology facilities or tools are common technology based items used in institutions of learning such as desktop computers, laptop, audio visuals devices, digital television, photocopy machines, overhead projector, internet, digital camera and so on.

ICT facilities have a great influence on teaching and learning at higher education level. Higher education institutions in so many countries including Nigeria have been spending large amounts of money in ICTs for over a long

period of time as integration of ICT in instructional procedure in higher education adds value to the whole teaching and learning process. (Siddiquah & Salim, 2017). According to UNESCO 2014, ICT improves learning of students, it aids the students to learn new skills set, promotes social mobility and has a multiplier effect across the education system.

Due to importance of ICT in the society and educational institutions, identifying the possible hindrances or challenges to integrating ICT in schools would be very important in improving the quality of teaching and learning in all levels of educational institutions in the country. Before implementing ICT based education and training, it is important to consider appropriate rooms or buildings available to house the technology, also worthy of note is the availability of electricity for smooth operation of the ICT facilities (Esoswo, 2011). Another major factor to consider is the availability of the ICT facilities which can be used for effective teaching and training. Teachers' ability to use ICT devices is greatly influenced by their attitude towards ICT. Their attitude is very significant because it controls their real behaviour. Wasilah et al, 2020, explains the attitude of an individuals as information about that individual's experience and personality to act in positive or negative way towards something. Lecturers' attitude and beliefs are crucial factors in determining the importance and effectiveness of ICT in their classrooms. Attitude and beliefs the lecturers hold or have about educational technology and pedagogy influences how he/she implement technology (Ertmer et al, 2012; Keengwe et al, 2008).

There is an obvious gap between being ICT competence or ability to use ICT for personal purpose and being competent in education to meet the educational goals of students for proper and successful use of ICT in education and training. It is important that the lecturers using ICT feel comfortable and confident about their ability to use them effectively in teaching their students (Leong et al, 2016).

Many educational institutions are showing support for increased levels of technology in the classrooms by providing hardware such as tablets and computers, enhanced internet facilities and connectivity, and implementing programs designed to improve computer literacy at various institutions of learning (Johnson et al, 2016). Despite the effort of various institutions, insufficient equipment or connectivity, inadequate professional development and training hinders technology implementation in classrooms. This is supported by Ibe (2021) who found out in his study that unstable power supply, high cost of teaching gadgets among others hinders utilization of ICT facilities in schools. Some of these problems could be institution based or individual based hence the need for this study.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to ascertain challenges in the use of ICT in agricultural education and training in colleges of education in Adamawa State. Specifically, to study sought to determine:

- i. availability of ICT facilities for agricultural education and training in colleges of education in Adamawa State.
- ii. attitude of agricultural education lecturers towards the use of ICT facilities in agricultural education and training in colleges of education in Adamawa State.
- iii. constraints in the use of ICT facilities in agricultural education and training in colleges of education in Adamawa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered by the study:

- i. What are the ICT facilities available for agricultural education and training in colleges of education in Adamawa State?
- ii. What are the attitudes of agricultural education lecturers towards the use of ICT in agricultural education and training in colleges of education in Adamawa State?
- iii. What are the constraints in the use of ICT in agricultural education and training in colleges of education in Adamawa State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- H₀₁ There is no significant difference in the attitude of lecturers from federal and state owned college of education towards the use of ICT in agricultural education and training in Adamawa State.
- H₀₂ There is no significant difference on the constraints faced by lecturers in federal and state owned college of education on the use of ICT in agricultural education and training in Adamawa State.

Methodology

The researcher adopted survey research design for the study. The population of the study comprise of 30 lecturers teaching students in Agricultural Education Department in Federal College of Education Yola (FCE) and 28 lecturers also teaching students in Agricultural Education Department in Adamawa State College of Education Hong (COE), making a total population of 58 lecturers. The whole population was used for the study due to their relative manageable sizes. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was made up of 2 sections A and B. Section A was on demographic data of the respondents while section B was made up of 3 sub-sections. Sub-section 1 was based on research questions one sub-section 2 and 3 were based on research questions two and three respectively. A checklist of 18 items was used to collect data on the availability of ICT facilities in the colleges of education. Research question 1 was structured on two responses which include: available and unavailable, and to effect decision, any percentage of up to 1 and above was considered as available and below 0 was considered as unavailable. Research question 2 and 3 were structured on a 4-point scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD), with corresponding value of 4, 3, 2 and 1. To effect decision on research question 2 and 3, any mean of 2.50 and above was considered as agree and any mean of less than 2.50 was considered as disagree. The instrument for data collection was validated by 1 expert in the Department of Vocational Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola and 3 experts from the Department of Vocational and Technical Education, Adamawa State University, Mubi. A copy of the instrument was given to the experts with the objectives of the study, research questions and hypotheses. Their observations and contributions were used to develop the final copy of the instrument. To determine the reliability of the instrument, the questionnaire was administered to 5 lecturers in Agricultural Education programme of the Department of Vocational and Technical Education, Adamawa State University, Mubi which were not part of the population of the study. The data collected was analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and a reliability coefficient of 0.76 was obtained through test re-test method. The questionnaire was distributed by the researcher and one research assistant to the respondents on one-on-one basis so as to ensure 100 percent retrieval of the questionnaire. The data collected was analysed using frequency count, mean and standard deviation to answer research

question one, two and three respectively while t-test statistic was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What are the ICT facilities available for agricultural education and training in colleges of education in Adamawa State?

Table 1: Frequency count on the Availability of ICT Facilities in Colleges of Education in Adamawa State

ICT Facility	COE (n=28)		FCE (n=30)	
	F	Remark	F	Remark
Desktop computer	7	Available	16	Available
Laptop computer	4	Available	25	Available
Ipads	0	Unavailable	0	Unavailable
Smart phones	3	Available	10	Available
Printer	8	Available	13	Available
Scanner	3	Available	9	Available
Photocopier	12	Available	20	Available
Projector	9	Available	20	Available
Digital camera	3	Available	0	Unavailable
Video recorder	4	Available	9	Available
Television	7	Available	10	Available
Radio	0	Unavailable	14	Available
Web camera	8	Available	5	Available
Internet services	0	Unavailable	28	Available
Public address system	7	Available	25	Available
e-library	6	Available	28	Available
Interactive white board	8	Available	9	Available
CBT software	0	Unavailable	3	Available

Table 1 showed the result on the availability of ICT facilities for agricultural education and training. From the result, facilities for ICT are available in state owned college of education except Ipads, internet services, radio and CBT software while federal college of education has an appreciable number of the facilities ranging from desktop and laptop computers, printers and scanners but lack ICT facilities which include Ipads and digital camera.

Research Question 2

What are the attitudes of agricultural education lecturers towards the use of ICT in agricultural education and training in colleges of education in Adamawa State?

Table 2: Attitudes of Agricultural Education Lecturers towards the Use of ICT in Agricultural Education and Training in Colleges of Education in Adamawa State

S/N	Items Statement	COE(n=28)			FCE (n=30)		
		Mean	SD	Remark	Mean	SD	Remark
1.	Lecturers are comfortable using ICT facilities in their classes	2.71	0.71	Agree	2.53	0.75	Agree
2.	Lecturers are acquainted with the internet	2.42	0.50	Disagree	3.33	0.47	Agree
3.	Lecturers develop online course materials	2.42	0.74	Disagree	2.50	0.93	Agree
4.	Lecturers are not motivated to use ICT facilities	2.89	0.68	Agree	3.06	0.58	Agree
5.	Most lecturers are not in favour of using ICT facilities	2.14	0.84	Disagree	2.90	0.40	Agree
6.	Lecturers feel ICT has insignificant impact on agricultural education and training	1.71	0.89	Disagree	2.16	0.94	Disagree
7.	Lecturers lack confidence to use ICT facilities	2.28	0.46	Disagree	2.16	0.59	Disagree
8.	Lecturers feel less in control of class when using ICT facilities	2.71	0.71	Agree	2.10	0.66	Disagree
9.	Resistance to technology by lecturers	2.52	1.10	Agree	2.06	0.82	Disagree
	Grand mean	2.42	0.74	Disagree	2.51	0.69	Agree

Result from table 2 presented result on attitude of agricultural education lecturers towards the use of ICT facilities in agricultural education and training in colleges of education in Adamawa State. The result revealed that agricultural education lecturers in both federal and state owned college of education are comfortable using ICT facilities in their classes with mean rating of 2.71 for COE and 2.53 for FCE, though not all category of respondents are acquainted with the use of internet and develop online course materials. Also, the result showed that agricultural education lecturers in both FCE and COE feels that ICT has an insignificant impact on agricultural education and training with a mean rating of 2.16 and respectively. Finally, lecturers in COE feels less in control of class and also agreed that there is resistant to technology as against the FCE lecturers.

Research Question 3

What are the constraints in the use of ICT in agricultural education and training in colleges of education in Adamawa State?

Table 3: Constraints in the Use of ICT in Agricultural Education and Training in Colleges of Education in Adamawa State

S/N	Items Statement	COE(n=28)			FCE (n=30)		
		Mean	SD	Remark	Mean	SD	Remark
1.	Problem of connectivity and speed	3.25	0.64	Agree	2.53	0.50	Agree
2.	Signal problem	2.92	0.53	Agree	2.33	0.75	Disagree
3.	No access to technical staff	3.10	0.49	Agree	2.63	0.96	Agree
4.	Agriculture Education curriculum not compatible with ICT	2.85	0.65	Agree	2.03	0.99	Disagree
5.	Lack of effective training	3.35	0.67	Agree	3.36	0.49	Agree
6.	Insufficient number of computers	3.57	0.50	Agree	3.30	0.65	Agree
7.	Load shedding (Poor electricity supply)	3.00	1.08	Agree	2.63	0.61	Agree
8.	Limited time for lectures	3.10	0.87	Agree	2.30	1.14	Disagree
9.	Lack of incentives	3.57	0.74	Agree	3.03	0.55	Agree
10.	Poor funding for ICT	3.60	0.73	Agree	3.00	0.69	Agree
11.	Lack of support from college management	3.14	0.65	Agree	3.00	0.83	Agree
Grand mean		3.22	0.71	Agree	2.74	0.86	Agree

Table 3 showed result on constraints in the use of ICT facilities in agricultural education and training in colleges of education in Adamawa State. From the result, both category of respondents agreed on the identified problems which include among others problem of connectivity and speed with mean of 3.25 for COE lecturers and 2.53 for FCE lecturers. Lack of incentives and access to technical staff was also identified by both category of respondents with mean of 3.57 and 3.03 by COE and FCE lecturers respectively. Poor funding has the highest mean of 3.60 in COE while lack of effective training has the highest mean of 3.36 in FCE.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the attitude of lecturers from federal and state owned colleges of education towards the use of ICT in agricultural education and training in Adamawa State.

Table 4: Mean Responses of Agricultural Education Lecturers on the Attitude of Lecturers towards the Use of ICT in Agricultural Education and Training in Adamawa State.

Attitude	Mean	N	Sd. Dev	Df	T	Sig	Decision
FCE	2.42	30	0.74	57	3.2	0.002	Reject
COE	2.51	28	0.69				

Table 4 showed results of the t-test analysis, it revealed that, there is significant mean difference between the attitude of agricultural education lecturers from federal and state owned tertiary institutions towards the use of ICT

facilities. [$t = 3.2$ (df 57), $P = 0.002$]. Since the computed p-value (0.002) is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected, therefore it is concluded that, there is significant difference between the attitude of agricultural education lecturers from federal and state owned tertiary institutions towards the use of ICT facilities in agricultural education and training.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference on the constraints faced by federal and state owned colleges of education on the use of ICT in agricultural education and training in Adamawa State.

Table 5: Mean Responses of Agricultural Education Lecturers on the Constraints Faced by Federal and State Owned Colleges of Education on the Use of ICT in Agricultural Education and Training in Adamawa State

Constraints	Mean	N	Std. Dev	Df	T	Sig	Decision
FCE	3.22	30	0.69	57	3.9	0.005	Reject
COE	2.74	28	0.75				

Table 5 presented results on constraints faced by agricultural education lecturers from federal and state owned tertiary institutions. It revealed that, there is significant mean difference between the constraints in the use of ICT facilities by federal and state owned tertiary institutions lecturers. [$t = 3.9$ (df 57), $P = 0.005$]. Since the computed p-value (0.005) is less than 0.05 level of significant, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected, therefore it is concluded that, significant difference exists between the constraints faced by federal and state owned tertiary institutions lecturer in the use of ICT facilities.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study on Table 1 showed that ICT facilities are available in both state and federal college of education in the state. In the state college, and out of the 18 ICT facilities considered, 14 were available while in the federal college of education, 16 were available. This finding is contrary to the findings of Habibu et al, (2012), who conducted a study on Difficulties faced by teachers in using ICT in teaching-learning at technical and higher educational institutions of Uganda, and found out that lack of software and hardware pose a challenge in the use of ICT in teaching and learning. This finding also disagree with the finding of Anandaraja et al, (2015), who also found out in their study that lack of facilities hinders the use of ICT to achieve information literacy in agriculture.

The finding of the study on Table 2 revealed that agricultural education lecturers from COE and FCE have a positive attitude towards the use of ICT in agricultural education and training. This finding agrees with the findings of Wasilah et al, (2020), who found out in their study that agricultural science teachers have good attitude to use of ICT to improve teaching. Similarly, the finding agrees with that of Nzomba and Nomsa (2018), who posited that teachers have positive attitude towards the use of ICT facilities in teaching agriculture.

The findings of the study on Table 3 revealed that problems which include connectivity and speed, signal problem, access to technical staff, lack of training and incentive, poor funding among others are the constraints in the use of ICT in

agricultural education and training in colleges of education in Adamawa State. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Ibe (2021), on challenges in the utilization of e-teaching in universities to include poor funding, unstable power supply and poor network. The finding also corresponds with that of Siddiquah and Salim (2017), Johnson et al, (2016) and Ahmed (2016) who all found out in their studies that poor connectivity and signal, poor electricity supply and funding are some of the constraints in the use of ICT in teaching.

In Table 4, findings of the study revealed that significant difference exist in the attitude of agricultural education lecturers from FCE and COE towards the use of ICT in agricultural education and training. This could be attributed to the fact that there are more facilities in FCE than COE which could influence their attitude. This finding is contrary to the findings of Ezhim et al, (2021) who found out from their study that COE lecturers' attitude in the use of ICT was favourable.

In Table 5, findings of the study revealed that significant difference exist on the constraints faced by COE and FCE lecturers on the use of ICT in agricultural education and training. This could also be traced to the fact that there are more facilities in FCE than COE, and also, there is difference in their funding based on the fact that federal tertiary institutions in the state are better funded compared to the state tertiary institutions.

Conclusion

The role of ICT in institutions of learning cannot be rivaled. ICT facilities have the capacity to improve instructional strategies there by improving the level of comprehension of students in colleges of education. Despite the roles ICT facilities play in teaching and learning, their availability is low in colleges of education most especially state owned colleges of education. The study revealed that agricultural education lecturers have positive attitude towards the use of ICT in agricultural education and training, but their level of availability pose a threat to the positive attitude of the lecturers. Similarly, constraints associated with the use of ICT facilities where they are available such as poor connectivity also pose a threat as it may frustrate lecturers when internet service is required for a particular purpose in the teaching process in agricultural education and training.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should make appropriate building available that will serve as ICT centre and also provide funds for procurement of ICT facilities.
2. Management of colleges of education at both federal and state level should not just use ICT facilities as a tool to pass National Commission for Colleges of Education accreditation but also make policies that will encourage their usage.
3. Collage management should make knowledge of ICT as a priority during recruitment off staff so as to have staff that are ICT compliant.

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